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***Employment Relationships, Automatic Decisions and their Limitations:
Regulating the incomprehensible phenomena***

Community provisions from the mid-1990s have triggered the current debate on the issue of possible limitations of automated decision-making systems in cases involving workers/employees because the final decision was rendered without human control and intervention. This issue has become extremely topical, especially in contemporary labor law. The aim of this research is to examine which regulatory strategies may be adopted in terms of automatic decision-making systems, based on complex mathematical processes that are beyond workers' comprehension. Given the huge advancement of such systems and their frequent use in employment relations, this issue has a considerable practical importance and has generated a growing interest in the legal debate. The aim of this paper is not to provide a technical analysis of existing solutions but to examine the possible responses of labor law to these regulatory strategies, in order to assess the appropriateness of various legislative options. The public availability of data would help workers/employees react accordingly. Yet, due to the complexity of the mathematical models and the nature of a civil trial, even if the companies presented the unreliable data, the said unreliability would never be discovered in ordinary judicial proceedings. So, which regulatory strategies can be adopted with automatic decision-making systems? The company must be free to use mathematical tools of its choosing for decision-making but the laws and regulations should divide the possible automatic tools into two categories: one left free for the unconditional application of the mathematical tools, and the other strictly regulated, because it pertains to the necessary protection of fundamental interests of the employee. The legal protection would be selective and

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would not concern all decisions but only those on crucial assets of extreme importance for the worker. This stronger but limited protection would force companies to compare their decisions on merits with mandatory regulatory standards.

Keywords: contemporary labor law, employment relationship, automated decision-making systems, business decisions, mathematical resources, employee and employer decisions.

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**RADNI ODNOSI, AUTOMATSKE ODLUKE I NJIHOVA
OGRANIČENJA: REGULISANJE NESHVATLJIVIH FENOMENA**

Propisi Evropske zajednice iz sredine 1990-ih pokrenuli su aktuelnu debatu o mogućim ograničenjima u upotrebi automatskih sistema za donošenje odluka u slučajevima koji se odnose na radnike/zaposlene, kada je konačna odluka doneta bez ljudske kontrole i intervencije. Ovo pitanje je izuzetno aktuelno, naročito u savremenom radnom pravu. Ovo istraživanje ima za cilj da ustanovi koje regulatorne strategije se mogu usvojiti u pogledu upotrebe automatskih sistema u donošenju odluka, budući da radnici/zaposleni ne razumeju njihove složene operativne (matematičke) procese. S obzirom na ubrzani razvoj takvih sistema i njihovu čestu upotrebu u oblasti radnih odnosa, ovo pitanje ima veliki značaj u praksi i privlači sve veće interesovanje u pravnom diskursu. Cilj ovog rada nije tehnička analiza postojećih rešenja već sagledavanje mogućih odgovora radnog prava na ove regulatorne strategije, kako bi se procenila prikladnost različitih zakonodavnih opcija. Javna dostupnost podataka bi pomogla zaposlenima da adekvatno reaguju. Međutim, čak i u slučaju kada bi kompanije dostavile nepouzdanе podatke, to nikada ne bi bilo otkriveno u redovnim sudskim postupcima zbog složenosti matematičkih modela i same prirode građanskog postupka. Dakle, koje regulatorne strategije se mogu primeniti kod automatskih sistema za donošenje odluka? Kompanija mora imati mogućnost slobodnog izbora u pogledu upotrebe matematičkih alata za donošenje odluka, ali zakoni i propisi treba da podele moguće automatske alate u dve kategorije: one koji omogućavaju bezuslovnu primenu matematičkih alata, i alate čija je primena strogo regulisana, s obzirom na neophodnu zaštitu osnovnih prava i interesa zaposlenog. Pravna zaštita bi bila selektivna i ne bi se odnosila na sve odluke, već samo na one o ključnog značaja za zaposlene. Ova snažnija ali ograničena zaštita bi primorala kompanije

da uporede svoje meritorne odluke sa obaveznim regulatornim standardima.

Ključne reči: savremeno radno pravo, radni odnos, automatizovani sistemi za donošenje odluka, poslovne odluke, matematički resursi, odluke zaposlenih i poslodavaca.